

Gamma Function Versus Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

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In (1), a gamma function $(e/T)^{k-1} \exp(-e/T)$ is proposed instead of the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\exp(-e/T)$. It is argued that there is not enough experimental data which verifies the MB distribution and so the gamma function may be studied.

Here we consider physical implications of the gamma function. We first note that a main idea of the MB distribution is that $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T)$ for an elastic collision $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. We note that gamma function retains this property, but only for energies near kT . We also note that given the integral $\int de \sqrt{e} \exp(-e/T)$, introducing an $(e/T)^{k-1}$ (as in (1)) does not change the form of the rising integral from $e/T=0$. It does, however, change the fall of the distribution, making it less steep as we show. Finally, we consider obtaining the gamma function distribution from an extremization of entropy and show that one no longer uses total energy sum over i $e_i p(e_i)=E_{total}$ as the constraint (which is a physical a priori constraint), but rather sum over i $p(e_i) \{ (k-1) \ln(e_i/T) - e_i/T \} = \text{number}$. We show that one may also consider reaction balance by replacing $p(e_i)$ with $p(e_i) / (e_i/T)^{k-1}$. In other words, two body scattering is more complicated under the gamma function scenario except for e_i/T values near 1.

Features of the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

The Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) distribution:

$$p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((1))$$

has several features such that it peaks for $e_i=0$. Nevertheless, integrating over available states $\int p dp \sqrt{e}$ introduces a factor of \sqrt{e} and so the overall integral does not drop from $e=0$ (as $\exp(-e_i/T)$ does), but rises. We are in fact interested in $e_i=T$ ($k=1$) as $E_{ave} = 3/2 kT$. We further note that $\exp(-e_i/T)$ drops off rapidly for $e_i/T \gg 1$.

A key feature of the MB distribution is that for any elastic collision:

$$\exp(-e_1/T) \exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-e_3/T)\exp(-e_4/T) \text{ for } e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4 \quad ((2))$$

We consider this an essential physical statement which suggests that as long as energy conservation holds in a 2-body collision, there is no preferred outcome pair. We argue that this feature must somehow be retained (at least in a certain e range) if one modifies the MB distribution.

Finally, we note that the MB distribution may be obtained through a maximization process by considering the two a priori constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((3a)) \text{ and } \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \quad ((3b))$$

There are my $p(e_i)$ sets which satisfy ((3a)), ((3b)). To obtain a unique set (based on extremization) one may consider a function:

Sum over i $p(e_i) f(p(e_i))$ where $f(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, the basic information ((4))

One may then argue that changing $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ yields an expression which contains no more information than the differentials of the two constraints ((3a)) and ((3b)). This leads to:

$p(e_i) df/dp(e_i) = 1$ (from Sum over i $dp(e_i) = 0$).

$dp f(p(e_i))$ is already matched with $e_i dp(e_i)$ ((5))

We now consider the proposed gamma function replacement for the MB distribution from (1).

Gamma Function Distribution

In (1) it is claimed that there is not enough experimental data to verify that the MB distribution is correct. They propose instead a gamma function distribution:

$(e_i/T)^{k-1} \exp(-e_i/T)$ ((6))

We wish to study the properties of this function in light of the properties considered in the previous section. We first note that the overall integral of the MB distribution contains a state piece of:

$\int \sqrt{e} de$ ((7))

Thus, ((6)) does not destroy the form of the overall integrand of de from rising from $e=0$. If $k > 1$, it rises more slowly.

The key informational feature ((2)), however, is violated. We argued above that it should hold at least for some range of e_i . We consider e_i values of $e_i = T$ ($k=1$). Consider:

$e_i/T = 1 + b$, where b is very small ((8))

Then: $(1+b)^{k-1} \exp(-1) \exp(-b) = 1 + (k-2)b$ ((8))

For a two body collision with $e_i/T = 1 + b_i$, one has:

$1 + (k-2)b_1 + (k-2)b_2 = 1 + (k-2)b_3 + (k-2)b_4$ ((9))

Thus, for $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((9)) allows all b_3, b_4 pairs which satisfy conservation with the same weight. Thus, this key feature holds, but only for a small range about $e_i/T = 1$.

Finally, we consider the drop-off of the gamma function for $e_i/T \gg 1$. Consider $e_i/T = B + b_i$ and $e_j/T = B$, where B is a large number. The ratio is:

$1 - b_i$ for the MB case, but $1 + b_i \{-1 + (k-1)/B\}$ for the gamma function ((9))

We note that $k=3/2$ to restore the average MB result as noted in (1). We see that in the MB case, one has a correction which is of the same order as that for the gamma function. Considering derivatives:

MB case: $d/dx \exp(-x) = -\exp(-x)$ ((10a))

Gamma case: $d/dx (x^{k-1} \exp(-x)) = -\exp(-x) x^{k-1} + (k-1) x^{k-2} \exp(-x)$ ((10b))

Here $x=e/T \gg 1$ and we consider $k=3/2$. The leading term of the gamma case is the first so $\exp(-x)$ is increased by the factor x^{k-1} and does not drop as fast. This then seems to be a key feature of the gamma distribution, we argue.

Maximization of Entropy

Maximization of entropy subject to a priori constraints is usually used to obtain the MB distribution. We have argued in previous notes, that one may consider the two a priori constraints:

Sum over i $p(e_i) = 1$ and Sum over i $e_i p(e_i) = e_{ave}$ ((11))

These allow for many $p(e_i)$ solutions. To choose a unique one, may consider the function:

Sum over i $p(e_i) f(p(e_i))$ where $f(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((12))

If one changes $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ and wishes to have the same value of the function, one may argue that the least information case is one in which the differentials of ((12)) match the differentials of the constraints ((11)). This leads to:

$dp(e_i) \ln(f(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T dp(e_i)$ or $\ln(f(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ ((13a))

And $p(e_i) df/dp(e_i) = 1$ or $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ for $p(e_i)$ unnormalized ((14)).

Mathematically, the gamma function conforms to the constraints:

Sum over i $p(e_i) = 1$ and Sum over i $p(e_i) \{ (k-1) \ln(e_i/T) - e_i/T \} = \text{number}$ ((15))

It is not clear why such constraints would be established in a priori manner, but if $\ln(f(p(e_i))) = (k-1) \ln(e_i/T) - e_i/T$, and $p(e_i) df/dp(e_i) = 1$, then:

$$p(e_i) = \exp \{ (k-1) \ln(e_i/T) - e_i/T \} \quad ((16))$$

In order to consider the above, one would require a physical reason for using Sum over i $p(e_i) \{ (k-1) \ln(e_i/T) - e_i/T \} = \text{number}$ as the a priori constraint of choice. This approach seems to suggest that ((2)) does not hold (which it doesn't except for e_i/T close to 1).

Another way to consider the problem is to use reaction balance. In the usual MB case, one uses:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4) \text{ and } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \quad ((17))$$

Here one may propose:

$$p(e_1) / (e_1/T)^{k-1} = p(e_2) / (e_2/T)^{k-1} = \text{same form with } e_3, e_4 \quad ((18)) \text{ and } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$$

$$\text{Then: } \ln\{ p(e_i) / (e_i/T)^{k-1} \} = -e_i/T \text{ or } p(e_i) = (e_i/T)^{k-1} \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((18))$$

For e_i/T almost 1, one has the usual MB two body interaction, but for e_i/T differing from 1, the collision product probabilities become more complicated.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that (1) proposes replacing the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution with a gamma function $p(e) = C (e/T)^{k-1} \exp(-e/T)$. We note that one should have the statistical informational property ((2)) for at least some range of e , and for the gamma function, it applies to e_i/T close to 1. This means that the usual $p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4)$ with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ only holds for all energy values e_i/T close to 1. The gamma function also has a slower drop-off with high e_i/T than the MB case, it seems. We show that the one may obtain the gamma function using maximization with an unusual constraint, but show that it appears readily from reaction balance if one replaces $p(e_i)$ with $p(e_i) / (e_i/T)^{k-1}$ suggesting a more complicated 2-body scattering interaction than $p(e_1)p(e_2)$.

References

1. Criss, E. and Hoffmeister, A. Incorporating Finite Particle Number and Heat-Temperature Differences in the Maxwell-Boltzmann Speed Distribuiton *Foundations* **2025**, 5(3), 29; <https://doi.org/10.3390/foundations5030029>
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